

The effects of EM-Bokashi compost and vegetable wastes compost on the growth of *Hibiscus esculentus* L. (lady's finger) plant

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Abstract:

Application of organic composts can improve soil quality as well as sustainability of agricultural production. This research concerns with the effects of EM-Bokashi compost and vegetable wastes compost on the growth of lady's finger plant. The experiment comprised two treatments viz., EM-Bokashi compost (soil:prepared EM-Bokashi = 1:1) and vegetable wastes compost (soil:organic matter such as tea and vegetables wastes = 1:1). Increase in the contents of moisture, organic carbon, humus and phosphorus were noticed in EM-Bokashi compost when compared to vegetable wastes compost. The contents of nitrogen and potassium were not much different from each other. The effects of EM-Bokashi compost and vegetable wastes compost on the growth of lady's finger plant such as plant height, circumferences of stem, number of fruits and leaves per plant were measured after 15 days, 30 days and 45 days. Plant height, stem circumference, number of leaves, yield and fruit size of lady's finger plant on EM-Bokashi compost was larger than vegetable wastes compost because EM-Bokashi compost has high organic carbon, humus and available phosphorus contents. In fact, the prepared EM-Bokashi compost can be used as a good source of nutrients for the plant growth and can reduce the farmer's budget for crop fertilization.

1. Introduction

In many countries large proportions of municipal waste are not disposed properly posing a potential environmental threat due to the presence of pathogens and toxic pollutants.¹ Organic municipal waste and other organic material such as manure can be composted. Composting is an action of encouraging the breaking down of organic waste. Composting is an aerobic process during which the organic matter is decomposed to humus-like substances. Composting can also be an anaerobic process, where breakdown occurs in the absence of oxygen. In this case, the main byproducts are methane, carbon dioxide and various low organic acids and alcohols. Since aerobic composting is more efficient and presents fewer undesirable by products.² Moreover, composting is the transformation of organic material (plant matter) through decomposition into a soil-like material called compost. Compost is an organic fertilizer that can be made on the farm at very low cost. Compost also helps the soil stay loose and easy to cultivate.³

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Sample collection

Soil sample was collected from the campus of Myeik University, Tanintharyi Region, Myanmar. In this research work, the soil from the upper position near to the surface about (15 cm) was digging in zigzag manner according to the sampling of soil samples.

2.2 Preparation of vegetable wastes compost

Vegetable wastes compost was prepared by using 1:1 weight ratio of the collected soil sample with vegetables wastes as green materials and tea residues as brown materials. A shady place under a thatched roof to protect the compost from the sun and rain was chosen. The soil mixture was added to earth pot and pushed in a stick in to mark the center of the pile. This pot was covered with plastic sheet.

After four weeks, turn the pile over to mix the different layers. The pile was watered for another week and then left for 8 weeks. Soils were incubated at 28 °C for eight weeks and rewetted to 70% of water

holding capacity. The pile was watered about three times a week. After eight weeks, vegetable wastes compost was obtained.

2.3 Preparation of effective micro-organism (EM), EM-Bokashi and EM-Bokashi compost

One bin of rice was dissolved in one liter of chlorine free water and stored at room temperature without direct sunlight. After seven days, the fermented rice water was mixed with milk (1:10 ratio). After two weeks, the yellow brown EM solution was obtained and stored in a cool dry place. The aqueous brown jaggery was added into the prepared EM solution and placed out of direct sunlight for 1-2 hours to allow the EM to activate more fully.⁴

Weight of ten lbs of rice bran was mixed with one spoon of brick powder, one spoon of salt, three liters of chlorine free hot water and 30 mL prepared EM and these mixtures were added in sack. The sack was tightly packed with rope and sit about two weeks in dark room at room temperature. After two weeks, gold yellow pleasant smell bokashi was obtained.

EM-Bokashi compost was prepared by mixing 1:1 weight ratio of the collected soil sample and prepared EM-Bokashi. After five days, EM-Bokashi compost was obtained.

2.4 Determination of physicochemical properties of prepared composts

The physicochemical properties and nutrients of prepared two composts were determined by conventional methods and modern techniques such as moisture content by oven drying method, pH by pH meter, soil texture by particle sizes analytical method, organic carbon and humus by titration methods, amount of soil nitrogen released by Kjeldahl method, content of available phosphorus by spectrophotometer, content of potassium by flame photometer, contents of exchangeable magnesium, calcium, potassium and sodium by using titration methods.

2.5 Plantation of lady's finger

Two experimental pots (13.5 inches diameter × 10.5 inches height) were prepared

and then vegetable wastes compost and EM-Bokashi compost were added into each pot. The Lady's finger was planted in the prepared two composts. The seeds were sowed at 2.5 cm deep on the pots. Two seeds were sowed in each planting hole. Seedlings emerged after 4 to 5 days of sowing. One healthy seedling was retained in each pot. After 2 weeks, only one healthy seedling per planting hold was left as shown in Figure 1. The plants were watered once a day every morning. The fruit is soft and crunchy to allow a continuous yielding; the plant must be planted at this stage. The effects of EM-Bokashi compost and vegetable wastes compost, on the growth of lady's finger plant such as plant height, circumferences of stem, number of fruits and leaves per plant were measured after 15 days, 30 days and 45 days. The NPK contents left in the soil were determined at 30 days, and 45 days.

Figure 1. Plantation of lady's finger in (a) vegetable wastes compost (b) EM-Bokashi compost

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Texture of prepared composts

The texture of vegetable wastes compost and EM-Bokashi compost were determined and the results are shown in Table 1. All prepared composts were loam type. Decrease in sand and clay percentage and increase in silt percentage were noticed in EM-Bokashi compost when compared to vegetable wastes compost. These increases might be related to the positive effect of microorganisms in EM-Bokashi compost.

Table 1. Texture of vegetable wastes compost and EM-Bokashi compost

Sample	Texture				Soil Type
	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	Total	
Vegetable Wastes Compost	39.55	41.90	17.05	98.50	Loam
EM-Bokashi Compost	38.65	46.75	13.35	98.75	Loam

3.2 Physicochemical properties of prepared composts

The physicochemical properties of two prepared composts were determined and the resulted data are shown in Table 2. The moisture percent of two composts were 1.07% and 1.78%, respectively. It was found that the higher moisture content due to the organic carbon content. When the organic carbon content was increased the soil porosity was increased and the moisture content was also increased. Increase in organic carbon content (4.60%) of EM-Bokashi compost was observed when compared to organic carbon content (3.26%) of vegetable wastes compost. The content of humus (7.93%) in EM-Bokashi compost was larger than vegetable wastes compost (5.62%). The higher the humus levels of the soil the greater the exchange capacity. Soil acidification may also occur by addition of hydrogen, due to decomposition of organic matter, acid-forming fertilizers, and exchange of basic cations for H^+ by the roots. Basic soils have a high saturation of base cations (K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Na^+). The higher the amount of exchangeable base cations, the more acidity can be neutralized in the short time perspective. The pH showed that vegetable wastes compost were acidic condition and EM-Bokashi compost was nearly neutral condition. This is because of EM-Bokashi compost has higher value of organic carbon and humus content. These parameters controlled the pH of prepared composts.

3.3 Contents of macronutrients of prepared composts

Contents of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium as macronutrients of plants

Table 2. Moisture, pH, organic carbon and humus contents of prepared composts

Sample	Moisture (%)	pH	Organic Carbon (%)	Humus (%)
Vegetable Wastes Compost	1.07	5.53	3.26	5.62
EM-Bokashi Compost	1.78	6.11	4.60	7.93

are shown in Table 3. The macronutrients in vegetable wastes compost on available N (0.23%), P (17.10 ppm) and K (22.62 mg/100 g) while macronutrients in EM-Bokashi compost on N (0.21%), P (20.14 ppm) and K (21.99 mg/100 g) were observed. Nitrogen helps plants with rapid growth, improving the quality of leaf and forage crops. Phosphorus in soil as inorganic phosphate ions and sometimes as soluble organic phosphorus can be absorbed and made available to meet plant. Plants need phosphorus for strong root growth, fruit, stem, disease resistance and seed development. The increase in phosphorus content of EM-Bokashi compost was observed by the greater multiplication of microbes. The nutrient, sometimes called potash, is essential for vigorous growth, disease resistance, fruit and general plant function.

Table 3. Contents of macronutrients of prepared composts

Sample	Total N (%)	P (ppm)	K_2O (mg/100 g)
Vegetable Wastes Compost	0.23	17.10	22.62
EM-Bokashi Compost	0.21	20.41	21.99

3.4 Exchangeable cation of prepared composts

Base saturation is the percentage of total CEC (negatively charged sites in the soils) occupied by the cations: Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ and K^+ . The ease with which plant roots can absorb cation nutrients increases with the degree of base saturation. The exchangeable

cations such as Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ and K^+ of prepared composts are shown in Table 4. Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ and K^+ values of vegetable wastes compost were 5.43, 1.99, 0.42 and 0.48 meq/100 g, respectively whereas in EM-Bokashi compost, they were 6.09, 2.71, 1.73 and 0.47 meq/100 g. It is still a little-known fact that calcium and magnesium amount determines how tight or loose soil is. The more calcium a soil has the looser it is; the more magnesium, the tighter it is, up to a point. A high calcium soil will have more oxygen drain freely and support more aerobic breakdown of organic matter, than a high magnesium. EM-Bokashi compost has higher calcium content than vegetable wastes compost.⁵

Table 4. Exchangeable cations in prepared composts

Sample	Exchangeable cations (meq/100 g)			
	Ca^{2+}	Mg^{2+}	Na^+	K^+
Vegetable Wastes Compost	5.43	1.99	0.42	0.48
EM-Bokashi Compost	6.09	2.71	1.73	0.47

3.5 Effect of vegetable waste compost and EM-Bokashi compost on plant height, stem circumferences and leaves

Data on growth parameters as plant height stem circumferences and number of leaves at 12 days, 15 days, 30 days and 45 days are shown in Table 5. During earlier growth period, *i.e.*, 12 days and 15 days, lady's finger plant in vegetable wastes compost had shown higher plant height, stem circumferences and number of leaves

Table 5. Effects of vegetable wastes compost and EM-Bokashi compost on plant height, stem circumference and number of leaves

Growth Parameter	Lady's Finger in Vegetable wastes Compost				Lady's Finger in EM-Bokashi Compost			
	12 days	15 days	30 days	45 days	12 days	15 days	30 days	45 days
Plant Height (inches)	5.0	5.2	8.7	29.5	4.0	4.5	9.6	35.5
Stem Circumference (inches)	0.6	0.7	1.2	2.3	0.4	0.4	1.1	2.5
Number of Leaves	4	4	10	18	3	5	11	24

whereas EM-Bokashi compost had significantly higher throughout the growing period, *i.e.*, on 45 days. The availability of nutrients in two composts was not too much differing from each other. However, organic carbon content and humus content in EM-Bokashi compost were much higher than the vegetable wastes compost. This situation favors the increase in the plant height and number of leaves over the vegetable waste compost.

3.6 Effect of vegetable wastes compost and EM-Bokashi compost on fruit yield and fruit size of lady's finger

Application of prepared composts had significant effect on fruit size, fruit circumference and fruit yield of lady's finger, as shown in Table 6. Fruit yield of lady's finger plant on EM-Bokashi compost was higher than that of vegetable wastes compost.

The EM-Bokashi compost is more important than inorganic fertilizer and vegetable wastes compost because it consists of relatively stable decomposed materials resulting from accelerated biological degradation of organic matter under controlled aerobic conditions.

From the experimental data, it was observed that the length of lady's finger in EM-Bokashi compost was longer than vegetable wastes compost and circumference of fruit was not too much different between two composts. This increase might be related to the positive effect of compost and microorganisms in increasing the root surface area per unit of

Table 6. Effects of vegetable wastes compost EM-Bokashi compost on fruit yield

Growth Parameter	Lady's Finger in Vegetable Wastes Compost	Lady's Finger in EM-Bokashi Compost
Fruit Length (inches)	5.4	6.0
Fruit Circumference (inches)	3.3	3.0
Number of Fruits per Plant	8	13

soil volume, water-use efficiency and photosynthetic activity, which directly affects the physiological processes and utilization of carbohydrates.^{6,7}

3.7 Comparison of NPK contents in prepared composts after 30 days and 45 days of plantation

The contents of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium in two prepared composts were found to be decreased after 30 days plantation. After 45 days plantation, contents of phosphorous and potassium in the prepared composts were lower than the values of original and 30 days after plantation. This is due to the fact that fruiting and seed formation requires higher phosphorous and potassium. However, total nitrogen content in the prepared composts had the same value as after 30 days (Table 7).

Table 7. NPK contents in prepared composts after 30 days and 45 days of plantation

Nutrients	Vegetable Wastes Compost			EM-Bokashi Compost		
	Before	30 days	45 days	Before	30 days	45 days
Total N (%)	0.23	0.20	0.20	0.21	0.18	0.18
P (ppm)	17.10	16.18	15.80	20.41	19.20	18.11
K ₂ O (mg/100 g)	22.62	16.39	16.10	21.99	15.30	14.25

4. Conclusion

The composting process is considered an economic and environmentally means to reduce the wastes such as

municipal and agricultural wastes going into landfill. The experiments were carried out from December 2016 to January 2017. The prepared vegetable wastes compost and EM-Bokashi compost have been characterized by conventional methods and modern techniques. The textures of two prepared composts were found to be loam type which can be suitable for plants. The pH (6.11) of EM-Bokashi compost was nearly neutral condition when compared to pH (5.53) of vegetable wastes compost. The contents of moisture (1.78%), organic carbon (4.60%) and humus (7.93%) of EM-Bokashi compost were larger than contents of moisture (1.07%), organic carbon (3.26%) and humus (5.62%) of vegetable wastes compost. It is indicated that EM-Bokashi compost can be used effectively as soil amended and this compost also can reduce the application of inorganic fertilizer. Macronutrient contents such as available P content was increased but total N and K contents were not much different in EM-Bokashi compost when compared to vegetable wastes compost. The lady's finger plants were planted in two prepared compost soils pots. Plant in EM-Bokashi compost treatment had significantly higher plant height, stem circumferences and number of leaves throughout the growing period after 30 days and 45 days plantation due to higher amount of organic carbon, humus and available phosphorous in EM-Bokashi compost. Moreover, the fruit length of lady's finger in EM-Bokashi compost was longer than vegetable wastes compost and fruit circumference was not too much different between two prepared composts. A slightly decrease in NPK contents EM-Bokashi compost after plantation. The findings indicated that EM-Bokashi compost as bio-compost can be used as fertilizer in agriculture and horticulture.

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